

Development and Validation of Frustration Scale for Emerging Adults

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was to develop an indigenous scale to measure frustration and to establish its psychometric properties. In the first phase, the item pool of 70 items was generated by an in-depth review of literature, and semi-structured interviews. Experts evaluation were taken to identifying the unclear, inappropriate, and redundant items. 17 items were excluded which were redundant, overlapped, or poor worded. Pilot study was conducted (n=20) on the preliminary scale to measure its face validity. In the second phase, internal consistency and dimensionality of the scale was empirically measured through Exploratory Factor Analysis (N=300). Three factors (Agitation, Liability, and Disgruntled) emerged. In the third phase, to confirm the factor structure of the scale the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (N=300) was run. Psychometric properties were established ($\alpha = .93$). In the final phase, the convergent and discriminant validity was established by using Basic Psychological Need Satisfaction and Frustration Scale (Vansteenkiste, 2015). Finally, indigenous frustration scale for emerging adults was constructed.

Introduction

Currently, Pakistani society is in the phase of paradigm shift. It is encountering changes in cultural norms, value and social fabric. Furthermore, the manifest acts of aggression, intolerance and frustrating behavior is frequently observed and experience in emerging adults (Abro, Fateh & Saeed, 2017). University going emerging adults are most susceptible to extremism and intolerance as evident from media reports. Which raises various questions about the causes, correlated and consequences (Mushtaq & Kiyani, 2013). Pakistan is facing complex social, economic and political challenges. While many problems such as poverty and energy crises are explicitly cited as key issues, but the fundamental problem concerns with the intolerant attitude of our emerging adults which significantly impacting their mental health (Zaman & Sabir, 2013).

Apart from geopolitical causes denial of basic human needs such as education, employment etc. leads individuals to become frustrated and unhappy. These circumstances fuel feeling of the dissatisfaction which cause irrational thinking and maladaptive behavior. Majority of emerging adults are influenced by those in their social circle who use violence and aggression to resolve their issues. Through social modeling, they learn that being intolerant is a way to maintain assertiveness and solve problems (Kaukab & Saeed, 2014).

It is obviously impossible to divide people into two groups, those who are frustrated and those who are not, for all frustrated to some extent (Carroll, 1993). Frustration is the situation in which the fulfilment of a motive is thwarted. In the other way frustration state is one of the personality characteristics (Sivakumar, 2018).

The value of the structure has led scholars of frustration to establish valid and accurate measures of frustration for emerging adults. With regard to mental health, social and career performance, frustration and academic can be calculated; as if a system is not objectively measured, it becomes empirically useless. Various scales are available for assessing frustration, but test-re-test reliability, internal consistency, and content, convergent, discriminant and predictive validity should be a helpful measure of frustration.

A generally accepted four component model of emotions has been suggested by Izard (1993). Izard (1993) defined the emotion on the basis of this model as a short lived, purpose-expressive phenomenon of feeling arousal. It may determine from this model that its need to consider all four components of frustration in order to understand frustration (i.e., subjective experience, physiological purposive and social-expressive element).

Anger and violence are emotions that are generally associated with frustration. In their work on the expressive aspect Gottman and Krokoff (1989) describe frustration as a low type of anger. Depression is the emotion widely associated with frustration (Powell, Honey & Symbaluk, 2016).

Many people are more susceptible to experiencing frustration. Research (Calkins et al., 2002) has shown that there are cognitive styles have important similarities. Calkins et al., (2002) have been able to group individuals into those who are easily frustrated and those who are less so. Degnan, Calkins and Keane (2008)

found that people were more likely to show more disruptive behavior (including aggression) if they had high reactivity to frustration and low physiological regulation (Eisenberg, Fabes, Nyman, Bernzweig & Pinuela, 1994). Harrington (2011) more recently argued that certain people suffer intolerance beliefs of frustration that leave them unstable and unable to work towards their personal goals. Harrington (2011) acknowledges that low self-confidence or perfectionistic cognitive styles are often simply masks of cognitive intolerance of frustration.

Hokanson and Burgess (1964) found that frustration increases boosts the level of excitement (with an increase in the heart rate of 20 beats per minute). Increased blood pressure was associated with frustration (Lewis, Hitchcock & Sullivan, 2004). Usually associated with frustration response, Suppressed Alpha Brain Waves (Jost, 1941), increased plasma corticosteroid level (Dantzer, Amone, & Mormede, 1980).

Frustration relates to the achievement, or rather non-attainment of a goal, according to Izard (1993) so the most appropriate context for determined the purpose and possible benefits of frustration is in the context of those theories related to goal motivated behavior such as operating conditioning (Powell, Honey & Symbaluk, 2016), expectancy theory (Bandura, 1997), and goal Setting Theory (Locke et al., 1981).

Rationale

The present study is aimed to develop an indigenous psychometric tool to measure frustration. Although, there are scales that are measuring frustration like Rosenzweig Picture-Frustration by Pareek, 1959; Reaction to Frustration Scale by Dixit and Srivastava, 1988; Frustration Tolerance by Rai, 1997; Frustration Test by Tiwari and Chauhan 1992; and Frustration Discomfort Scale by Harrington, 2005 were published. But existing scales of frustration have been developed in a different culture. But the items of these scales are not culture free, as culture of Pakistan is relatively a different culture from Europe and America and other individualistic cultures. The Reliable and valid indigenous measure of frustration is not available for Pakistani culture. Therefore, this study will develop an indigenous scale to measure frustration by including the key concept from prior literature refining them where necessary and linking them together with the emerging adults' perspective. The aim of this thesis is to develop a valid outcome measure of frustration for the emerging adults that is meaningful, and practical to implement. In all over the world, the effect of frustration is studied. However, very few researches are conducted in Pakistan on frustration, for which unavailability of the indigenous scale of frustration could be a major reason. The present research work is intended to fill the gap by developing a native scale of frustration.

Objectives

1. To develop an indigenous scale to measure emotions related to frustration for Emerging Adults.
2. To validate the Indigenous Frustration Scale (IFS) and establish its psychometric properties.

Methods

The study was conducted in following two phases:

Phase I: Development of Indigenous Frustration Scale (IFS)

Identification of construct and phenomenology of frustration was developed by review of previous literature, themes recognized through the participant's responses in the semi-structured interviews.

Item generation: These following steps made the conceptual basis available for the initial phrasing of the items.

Review of relevant literature: The first and foremost step in conceptualizing the phenomenology of frustration was to conduct an exhaustive and extensive review of literature. Therefore, the literature regarding frustration was reviewed carefully. The current progress in the field of frustration was evaluated and assessed to get an idea about the background of the construct. All the theories describing and explaining frustration was examined. It was comprehended how frustration have been explained by different psychologists and theorists. At the same time, the previous scales measuring the same construct were appraised in term of their utility, advantages, and limitations. The construct of frustration was conceptualized fully. The initial work for the development of the phenomenology of frustration was conducted.

Semi-structured interviews: During the second step in conceptualizing the construct, semi-structured interviews were conducted. Convenience sampling technique was used to select the sample. The sample was taken from different private and government universities. Permission and consent was taken from the experts to conduct the interview. The interviews were carefully transcribed. The respondents were asked to report their personal opinion about the frustration. Themes related to frustration were thoroughly identified.

The themes that emerged from semi-structured interviews were incorporated with those identified through literature review to make an item pool for scale construction. Finally, an item pool of 70 statements representing emotions related to frustration was formed based on the theme extracted and explored through careful observation, in-depth analysis and thorough appraisal of preceding the literature, profound evaluation of semi-structured interviews.

Expert Evaluation of the Item. The item pool of 70 statements constructed for indigenous frustration scale was presented to the experts for the purpose of evaluation. They were asked to discard the item that seemed to be irrelevant to the area of research. They were also requested to give their expert opinion for identifying repetition of the statement, double-barreled, poor worded and overlapping items. The experts were also requested to suggest any modification in the wording of the statements to improve the quality and

meaningfulness of the statement. 17 items were excluded which were redundant, overlapped, or poor worded. The experts' opinion revealed that 5 items needed to be modified to improve the quality of the statements.

Pilot Study. Pilot study was conducted to build up face validity of the scale and to ensure its understandability to the sample. A sample of 20 Emerging Adults both men (n=10) and women (n=10) was selected through convenience sampling technique. The sample age, ranged from 18-25 years (M= 20.08, SD= 5.02). The item pool consisting of 53 items was then arranged into a response format on a dichotomous scale. The respondents were required to respond each statement on a scale from 0 to 1 where, 1 was considered as *yes* with the item and 0 was considered as *no*. the items were then pilot tested (N=20) on both men and women. No ambiguity was found in the understandability of the items. Therefore, all the 53 items were retained in IFS.

Establishing construct validity through factor analysis. The construct validity was determined by applying Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA). The main objective was to explore the internal factor structure and dimensionality of IFS and ultimately finalize the scale items.

Sample. Cross-sectional research design was used to conduct the study. Convenience sampling technique was used to collect data for running EFA.

As the scale was developed for the emerging adult population, therefore, participants with age ranging from 18-25 years were included in the study.

A sample of 300 emerging adults with age 18-25 year (M= 20.69; SD= 1.79) including Males (n= 127) and Females (n= 173) were requested from seven universities (Quaid-e-Azam University, Islamic International University Islamabad, FUUAST, NUML, Arid University, FURC, FJWUR) of Rawalpindi/Islamabad. Universities of Islamabad generally have the representation of students from all provinces of Pakistan. Convenient sampling technique was used to collect the data from sample. The sample was selected keeping in view the criteria given by (Field, 2005; Nunnally, 1978; Comery & Lee, 1992; Kass & Tinsley, 1979) having between 5 and 10 participants per item.

Procedure. Data was collected from university students. At first authority permission was sought from the head of institution. Participants were approached for group administration in central libraries of universities. After having their consent, the scales were handed over to the respondents. They were asked to read each statement carefully and respond honestly to all items of the scales.

Results. To examine the factor structure, EFA was performed by using SPSS 23 version. Initially, the factorability of preliminary 53 items were examined. Several well-recognized criteria were adopted for the factorability of the items. The items were measured on dichotomous scale with 1= yes, and 0= no. for dimensionality of IFS, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) with Direct Oblimin Rotation method was employed. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy was .87 and Bartlett's test of Sphericity was significant $\chi^2(298) = 2459.550, p < .000$, which specify that the correlations between items were sufficiently large for running PCA. Next the communalities were all above .30; further confirming that each item shared some common variance with other items. Given these overall indicators, factor analysis was deemed to be suitable with all 53 items.

Results indicated that the factor 1 has an Eigen value of 6.75 and explain 25.01 of the total variance, factor II has an Eigen value of 1.58 and explain 5.83 variance; factor III has Eigen value of 1.41 and explain 5.15 of the total variance. Consequently, three components in the final analysis were retained. A total of 26 items are eliminated because they do not contribute to the simple factor structure and has cross-loading (see Table 1). Therefore, these items are not included in the final scale. As a result, 27 items are kept in the scale (see Table 1). All remaining items have factor loading above .35 in respective factor (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2001). All the items of IFS significantly correlate with the total score on IFS. All correlation values range between .86-.57 at $p < .01$. All the values are found to be significant as these are above .30 (Nunnally, 1994).

Indigenous Frustration Scale (IFS; Final Version)

The final scale comprised of 27 items and it has three factors. The items were selected based upon acceptable factor loadings (see Table 1).

Table 1
Factor Loading for Indigenous Frustration Scale for Emerging Adults through Principal Component Analysis by Using Direct Oblimin Rotation Method (N=300)

Sr. No	Item No in Initial Form	Item No in Final Form	F1	F2	F3	h^2
1	50	26	.70	.02	.03	.50
2	40	21	.63	.00	.03	.41
3	44	23	.57	.00	.02	.33
4	30	12	.53	.14	.07	.40
5	20	8	.40	.18	.09	.30
6	41	22	.38	.16	.13	.27
7	15	6	.35	.03	.29	.30

8	33	15	.06	.81	.05	.59
9	34	16	.09	.60	.00	.41
10	12	4	.28	.50	.39	.44
11	32	14	.33	.48	.21	.36
12	47	24	.03	.45	.27	.34
13	51	27	.04	.43	.11	.41
14	27	11	.10	.43	.00	.23
15	31	13	.16	.41	.09	.29
16	24	9	.12	.39	.06	.23
17	48	25	.29	.39	.12	.39
18	14	5	.11	.06	.54	.32
19	11	3	.08	.16	.53	.33
20	1	1	.14	.05	.51	.24
21	39	20	.12	.01	.51	.37
22	36	18	.13	.01	.49	.30
23	38	19	.33	.11	.46	.42
24	18	7	.18	.14	.45	.24
25	25	10	.04	.31	.43	.36
26	3	2	.28	.18	.41	.27
27	35	17	.17	.20	.39	.37
Eigen Value			6.75	1.59	1.41	
% of Variance			25.01	5.83	5.15	
Cumulative %			25.01	30.84	36.00	

Note. Factor Loading > 0.35 have been reported in each factor.

The description of each factor explained in table 1 is as follow.

Factor I: Agitation: 7 items (6,8,12,21,22,23,26) were loaded on this factor. The items include on this factor indicate how frustration relate with Agitation, such as resentment, restlessness, fixation, insecurity, hopelessness, and burdened. The score range on this scale from 7-28. High score means high level of frustration experience in emerging adults.

Factor II: Liability: 10 items (1,4,9, 13,14,15,16,24,25,26) were loaded on this factor. Items loaded on this factor include tendency to react towards frustrated situation. Usually people become irritated, disturbed, upset, depress, negative thoughts, disappointed, tensed, guilt, and unstable. The score range on this scale from 10-40. Higher the score means high level of frustration experience in emerging adults.

Factor III: Disgruntled: 10 items (1,2,3,5,7,10,17,18,19,20) loaded on this factor include the tendency to have Disgruntled behavior in frustrating situation. Different frustrating situation affects the emerging adults' mood negatively. The score range on this scale is from 10-40. High score means high level of frustration experience in the emerging adults.

Phase II: Establishing Psychometric Properties of IFS

The aim of this phase was to establish the psychometric properties of IFS. It was conducted in the following two stages.

1. Confirmatory Factor Analysis
2. Convergent and Discriminant Validity

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA). In this section of the study, the 27 items with three factors explored through EFA were analyzed using CFA to confirm the factor structure of the measurement model of IFS. The aim of this study was to confirm dimensionality and factor structure of the scale; analysis was done through AMOS 22.

Sample. Cross-sectional research design was used to conduct the study and convenience sampling technique was used to select the sample. Participants' age ranged 18-25 year were included. The sample size was selected according to the criteria of 5 to 5 respondents per item (Tabachnick&Fidell, 2001). According to this criteria, 300 was an adequate sample size. The sample of the present study consisted of n=149 females and n=151 males' university students.

Instrument. Along final version of IFS, Basic Psychological Need Satisfaction and Frustration Scale (BPNSFS) by Vansteenkiste (2015) was also administered to determine convergent and discriminant validity of IFS. The BPNSFS is composed of two separate scales that measure the Need Satisfaction and Need Frustration of the individual and gives a separate score of Need Satisfaction (NS) and Need Frustration (NF). The NS and NF have been proved to be two different and opposite dimension (Vansteenkiste& Ryan, 2013). This scale was selected to measure the convergent and discriminant validity of IFS. The BPNSFS is a 24 item scale. It has six subscales, Autonomy Satisfaction, Autonomy Frustration, Relatedness Satisfaction, Relatedness Frustration, Competence Satisfaction, and Competence Frustration. Three subscales (Autonomy Satisfaction, Relatedness

Satisfaction, Competence Satisfaction) measure NS and three subscales (Autonomy Frustration, Relatedness Frustration, Competence Frustration) measure NF. It is a Likert type scale ranging from 1 (Not true at all) to 5 (Completely true).

Procedure. Permission for the use of BSNSFS (Vansteenkiste, 2015). Was taken from the author. The data were collected through convenient sampling technique. Data was collected from university students online with the help of Google form. 500 students were approached, but only 300 students filled the forms. Participants were given directions to read all instructions carefully and complete both questionnaires carefully; not to skip any item. Informed consent was taken and confidentiality was ensured. Once the forms were filled, the data was subjected to further analysis.

Results. The factor structure of the IFS was analyzed to describe the model fit indices with $\chi^2 = 659.889$, $df = 298$. The measurement model (3 factors) has been fit indices to the data set, that is $\chi^2 / df = 2.22$, RMSEA = .04, TLI = .98, NFI = .99, GFI = .94, CFI = .95; all of these indices surpass the satisfactory limit of $\chi^2 / df < 3$, RMSEA= Root Mean Square Error of Approximation $\leq .06$, CFI = Comparative Fit Index $\geq .90$, TLI = Tucker-Lewis Index $\geq .90$, GFI=Goodness of-Fit Index $\geq .90$, NFI= Normed Fit Index $\geq .90$ (Hayduk, 2015; Kline, 2013).

Figure 1. Model obtained through confirmatory factor analysis for IFS

The figure 1 shows the factor loadings of items achieved through CFA. The final good fit CFA model comprised of 26 items with 3 factors. Hence, the factor structure developed through EFA was confirmed by applying CFA. Figure 1 reflects the factor loadings of each indicator and regression weights of covariance.

Table 2
Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient and Correlation Matrix among 3 Subscales of IFS (N=300)

Scales	No of Items	α	IFS	Agitation	Liability	Disgruntled
Indigenous Frustration Scale	27	.93	-	-	-	-
Agitation	7	.81	.83**	-	-	-
Liability	10	.87	.86**	.59**	-	-

Disgruntled	10	.80	.84**	.59**	.57**	-
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** $p < 0.01$

The results in table 2 reveal that there is a strong positive correlation between IFS and its subscales. The total scores of IFS are highly correlated with its all 3 subscales. The reason for this high correlation is that all the subscales of emotions related to frustration are measuring one or another emotion (Raykov&Marcoulides, 2011; Piedmont, 2014), however the intercorrelation among subscales is between .57 and .86 at $p < 0.0$. The correlation matrix demonstrates its internal consistency (Nunnally, 1994).

Table 3

Descriptive Statistics and Alpha Reliability Coefficients for Scales and Subscales (N=288)

Scales	Items	M	SD	Kurt	Skew	Potential	Actual
IFS	26	69.45	11.19	.05	.23	26-130	27-120
Agitation	7	17.31	5.06	-.02	.16	7-35	7-32
Liability	9	25.87	7.38	-.20	.27	9-45	9-44
Disgruntle	10	23.71	5.64	.11	.09	10-50	10-40

Note: M=Mean, SD=Standard Deviation, Kurt= Kurtosis, Skew= Skewness, IFS= Indigenous Frustration Scale.

Table 3 shows the descriptive, alpha, skewness, kurtosis and other psychometric properties of the scales. As evident from the table, all the alpha reliabilities of all the scales were deemed acceptable and satisfactory, that is ranged from .93 to .69. They have exceeded the cutoff value of .70 as recommended by Pallant (2013). Values of Skewness and Kurtosis were within the acceptable range of +1 to -1 (Hayduk, 2015), there by indicating the normality distribution of data.

The second step of phase II was establishing scale's validity. The aim was to validate IFS so it could be applied in practical settings to measure the individuals' frustration level. For this reason, the scales' convergent and discriminant validity was explored. It was hypothesized that the scores of IFS will converge with the NF and discriminant with NS scores on BPNSFS (Vansteenkiste, 2015).

Multicollinearity was tested through Tolerance Test and Variance Inflation Factor (VFI). Tolerance value should not be < 0.1 and VFI (opposite of tolerance) should not be > 10 (Fox, 1991). In this study tolerance values of all our measure such as IFS (.24), NS (.65) NF (.72) was greater than 0.10 which suggests that there was no multicollinearity in data (Pallant, 2020). Correspondingly, VIF (opposite of tolerance) value of all the measures that is IFS (3.52), NS (.2.43), and NF (4.72) was less than 10 which also suggest that there was no issue of multicollinearity.

Analysis was performed to ensure the robustness of the scale and to establish the convergent and discriminant validity of the proposed IFS with similar and related scale NS AND NF of BPNSFS. According to Lyubomirsky and Lepper (1999), discriminant validity is not suitable for validation of psychological scales; nevertheless, this technique is still in practice for establishing the robustness of proposed scales. The results demonstrated that none of these constructs had significant association with our IFS and it stands out as a distinct scale.

Table 4

Overall Reliability and Validity of the Construct (N=300)

	CR	AVE	MSV	IFS	NS	NF
IFS	.90	.45	.37	.71		
NS	.85	.42	.23	.54	.65	
NF	.83	.44	.17	.33	.22	.70

Note. Values of squared root estimate of AVE are boldfaced. AVE = Average Variance Extracted; MSV = Maximum Shared Variance; CR = Composite Reliability; IFS = Indigenous Frustration Scale; ND = Need Satisfaction; NF = Need Frustration.

Convergent and Discriminant Validity. Further, convergent and discriminant validity is also assessed through CFA. Fornell and Larcker (1981) criteria for validity evaluation is followed for this purpose. CR and AVE are used for evaluation of convergent validity. Values of composite reliability of all construct, that is IFS (.90), NS (.85), and NF (.83) are more than .70.

Additionally, the AVE values of IFS (.45), NS (.42), and NF (.44) are less than .50. In this study, CR of for NF is greater than .70 this means that the convergent validity of NF was adequate, thus, fulfilling the concept of convergent validity. Similarly, discriminant validity is also supported as the square root value of AVE for all the

measure that is IFS (.71), NS (.65), and NF (.70) are greater than their matching squared correlation (Fornell&Larcker, 1981). Thus the criteria for both convergent and discriminant validity are maintained.

Discussion

The present study was designed to develop an indigenous Frustration Scale for emerging Adults. The model of four component emotions of Izard (1993) provided the conceptual foundation for the generation of items for the scale. The researcher followed Izard model of four component emotions, because it is well established, multidimensional, and covers almost all aspects of frustration and it is a mixed model approach. There is a variety of existing self-report frustration scales, being applied all over the world to measure frustration as a reaction rather than an emotion. Among all scales of the frustration, not even a single valid scale developed and published in Pakistani cultural context is available in the country. Therefore, this study was an attempt to develop Indigenous Scale of Frustration.

The output of EFA produced the three factor model solution consisting of 27 items. Items reflecting theoretical relevance with each other in a factor with eigenvalue 1 and loading of .35 or beyond were retained. The EFA results of the present study also indicated that most of the item have sufficient loading on more than one factor. These findings are consistent with Costello and Osborne (2005) who articulated that strong data requires multiple variables loading strongly on to the factors. The results also showed that item communalities are ranged from .42 to .74. this range is considered to fit within the low to moderate range typical of social science research according to Costello and Osborne (2005). The results also showed that there is no item with cross loadings surpassing .32. These loadings satisfy the criteria frequently cited by Tabacknick and Field (2007) as the minimum requirement for avoiding items that have overlapping variance on multiple factors.

Through the judges' opinion these factors were given titles as factor 1 (Agitation), factor 2 (Liability) and factor 3 (Disgruntled). Agitation factor had 7 items that loaded at the ranged from .70 to .35. This factor includes (resentment, restlessness, fixation, overloaded, insecurity, hopelessness, and burdened) which express frustration among the emerging adults. These items suggested that Agitation experienced by the emerging adults as a result of frustration. According to DSM V Agitation behavior include symptoms such as hopelessness, restlessness, resentment, and etc. Results of the present study was consistent with Beasley and Pamela (2007) research in which agitation refers to the behaviors that fall along a continuum ranging from the verbal threats and motor restlessness to harmful aggressive and destructive behaviors. Other researchers also define agitation as a feeling of irritability or severe restlessness. It is a common sight that most of the emerging adults have been addressing it frequently (Siddiqui, Gupta, & Huecker, 2020).

Second factor Liability had 10 items that loaded at the ranged from .81 to .39. This factor includes (disturbed, upset, depressed, negative thoughts, disappointed, tensed, guilt, unstable, crying spells, and irritation) emotions of frustration. These items express emotional liability in the emerging adults during frustration. In medicine and psychology, liability is a sign or symptom typified by the exaggerated changes in mood or affect in quick succession (Posner, Jonathan; Kass, Erica; Hulvershorn, Leslie, 2014). The person experiencing emotional liability usually feels like he/she does not have control over his/her emotions. Items of this factor were also consistent with Kim and Jong (2016) research which suggested that emotionally labile emerging adults experience or display frequent unusually intense and negative emotions in response to events and experiences, emotions which are unpredictable and swing wildly.

Third subscale Disgruntled, it refers to frustration emotions like anxious, burnout, aggression, dissatisfaction, boredom, fear, intolerance, stacked, and give up. These findings are supported by previous literature (Powell, Honeg&Symbaluk, 2013) reported anxious, sadness, depression, and stress as an emotion commonly associated with frustration.

In order to confirm the factor structure and dimensionality of the scale CFA was run. The results demonstrate that the measurement model proved to be the best fit model for the scale with acceptable model fit indices that surpass the satisfactory limits of all required indices (Hu & Bentler, 1999). The final scale comprised of 26 items with 3 well defined factors. Hence, the factor structure developed through EFA was confirmed by applying CFA (Visvizi& Nawaz, 2020).

To further establish psychometric properties, alpha reliability of the scale and its subscales was measured. The Alpha reliability of IFS ranged between .93 to .81. As most of the emotions were overlapping in different construct, therefore, only items fitting into one factor were retained that has resulted in high alpha reliability. The subscales show significantly high correlation with each other and the total score of IFS, hence, are measuring the same construct (Nunnally, 1994).

The scale was validated using BPNSFS (Vansteenkiste, 2015). The convergent and discriminant validity was successfully established by taking Composite Reliability and Average Variance Extracted (Fornell&Larcker, 1981). The results demonstrated that none of these constructs (NS & NF) had significant association with the IFS. IFS stands out as a Distinct scale.

Limitations and Suggestions

The study was carried out as a part of large study of development and validation of indigenously constructed frustration scale. So bi-variate correlational analysis between frustration and need satisfaction was carried out. This study could be more interesting by introducing more predictors and outcome variables. The study has limited generalizability in the sense that sample was collected from the one city only, and hence, ignored all the other provinces. Sample from all over the country should be selected in future studies. It would have been better if incremental validity of the frustration could be measured in this study, but it could not be possible due to time constraints. So the limitation should be kept in mind while replicating the study in future. Data collection was based on the convenient sampling without any control over variables that might affect the factor structure of the scale. The sample was also heterogeneous; more homogeneous sample could be drawn in future studies to ascertain construct validity of IFS. Due to shortage of time, this study did not develop norms for new scale. Further study should be conducted to develop norms of a Pakistan population. Sample size was small. It should have been at least 10 times greater than total number of the items (Nunnally, 1978), more stable factor structure would have been generated. The scale has been developed with an emerging adults sample (age 18-25). It might be that, frustration causes, impacts, and their way of expression be different in middle and late adulthood. So the scale should be tested on the above sample. EFA and CFA was applied to establish the internal structure of the scale, still there is need to replicate factor structure with other samples to establish the psychometric characteristics of IFS. The current study has not explored clinical sample. The scale needs to be validated for the diagnostic purpose in clinical settings.

Conclusion and Implications

Research on frustration is in the embryonic stage in Pakistan and many areas need to be explored. It is professional duty of researchers to grasp the deeper understanding of the concept. This study provides an indigenous, quantitative, comprehensive, and less time consuming scale for measuring frustration of Pakistan population. The scale has been developed catering the cultural aspects of Pakistan population. IFS can be used for the emerging adults' frustration in their social, cultural, physical, psychological, occupational, and health settings.

The scale can be useful in investigating the effects and outcomes of frustration in individuals' life. The feedback of frustration can be used as a baseline to incorporate more psychological issues, like depression, anxiety, stress, and etc.

This valid and reliable scale can be use in all sectors and walks of life in screening individual on their frustration level. It can also work as a feedback system for individuals as well to regulate their goals accordingly. For clinicians it can work as a base line to get an idea about patients' frustration level and plan intervention accordingly. This psychometric tool can prove to be a landmark in the developmental field of psychology in Pakistan by emerging as a first tool to measure frustration in Pakistan population. The scale can further be used in intervention based studies.

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